

The OCEANA logo is positioned in the top left corner. It features a white circular icon with a stylized wave or fish shape inside, followed by the word "OCEANA" in a bold, white, sans-serif font. The background of the entire page is a collage of blue-toned images: a large school of fish in the upper left, a boat with several people on the water in the middle, and various fish and fish products in the lower right. A grid of white and orange lines is overlaid on the background, creating a technical or data-like aesthetic.

OCEANA

NET LOSS

HOW GOVERNANCE
GAPS ARE SINKING
PHILIPPINE
FISHERIES

About Oceana Philippines International

Oceana is the largest international advocacy organization dedicated solely to ocean conservation. Oceana is rebuilding abundant and biodiverse oceans by winning science-based policies in countries that control one-quarter of the world's wild fish catch. With more than 325 victories that stop overfishing, habitat destruction, oil and plastic pollution, and the killing of threatened species like turtles, whales, and sharks, Oceana's campaigns are delivering results. A restored ocean means that 1 billion people can enjoy a healthy seafood meal every day, forever. Together, we can save the oceans and help feed the world. Visit [Oceana.org](https://oceana.org) to learn more.

Philippine Office address: P.O. Box 255, UP Post Office, University of the Philippines Diliman Campus, Diliman, Quezon City 1101

Email address: philippines@oceana.org

About this Report

This narrative report was prepared by Emmanuelle Tiña Magno on behalf of Oceana Philippines International for key policy leaders and decision-makers in the Philippine government, fisherfolk communities, and advocates. The report is based on the comprehensive study "Philippine Fisheries Assessment: A Glimpse of RA 10654's 10-Year Implementation" by Alice Joan G. Ferrer, Wilfredo L. Campos, and Harold M. Monteclaro, published in 2026.

Editors: Rose Liza Eisma-Osorio, Nikka Oquias, Christine Dar-Sicada, Diovanie de Jesus, Danny Ocampo, Joyce Sierra

Design and Layout: Mark Kevin de Guia

Design Lead: LA Villavicencio

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18320988

The views in the report represent those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the views of the above organization.

IN THIS REPORT

- 4 **EXECUTIVE SUMMARY**
- 7 **CHAPTER 01: INTRODUCTION**
- 8 **CHAPTER 02: PRODUCTION TRENDS AND STOCK STATUS**
- 13 **CHAPTER 03: MANAGEMENT INTERVENTIONS AND EFFECTIVENESS**
- 20 **CHAPTER 04: ENFORCEMENT AND COMPLIANCE**
- 25 **CHAPTER 05: INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY – BFAIR PERFORMANCE**
- 29 **CHAPTER 06: LOCAL GOVERNMENT IMPLEMENTATION**
- 36 **CHAPTER 07: SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS OF FISHERFOLK**
- 42 **CHAPTER 08: CONCLUSIONS**
- 46 **CHAPTER 09: RECOMMENDATIONS**

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

For the past forty years, Philippine fisheries have been in documented decline. The situation has now reached a critical juncture that demands immediate and coordinated action. Despite the existence of comprehensive legal frameworks intended to sustainably manage Philippine fisheries, including the 1998 Fisheries Code and its 2015 amendment (RA 10654), capture fisheries production has been decreasing by an average of 45,472 metric tons annually since 2010. The data even after the implementation of RA 10654 reveal persistent challenges: while adequate policies exist, systemic constraints at every governance level along with bureaucratic inertia are preventing effective implementation of these laws. Without urgent intervention to address these issues, the decline will continue, threatening both marine ecosystems and the livelihoods & food security for millions of Filipinos dependent on fisheries.

Historical Context

This assessment examines the challenges in the implementation of fisheries management in the Philippines. The timeline spans from the 1978 peak in per capita capture production, through scientific documentation of maximum sustainable yield breaches in the 1980s, to the 2010 production decline that continues today.

RA 10654 amended the 1998 Philippine Fisheries Code in 2015, strengthening provisions for ecosystem-based management, vessel monitoring, and enforcement. FAO 263 established 12 Fisheries Management Areas in 2019, dividing Philippine waters based on fisheries ecosystems rather than political boundaries. Despite these developments, the Supreme Court issued its 2024 ruling on the Mercidar case, nullifying the 15-kilometer delineation for municipal waters and allowing

commercial fishers to operate in those waters. This undermines the preferential rights of small-scale fisherfolk in municipal waters. Additionally, legal challenges to FAO 266 have stalled progress in full implementation of vessel monitoring measures (VMM), complicating enforcement efforts.

MERCIDAR CASE – COMMERCIAL ACCESS INTO MUNICIPAL WATERS

In December 2024, the Supreme Court upheld the Malabon Regional Trial Court's decision allowing Mercidar Fishing Corporation's commercial vessels to operate in municipal waters—areas traditionally reserved for small-scale fishers under RA 10654.

The ruling declared key provisions of RA 10654 that restricted commercial fishing in municipal waters as unconstitutional, effectively shifting regulatory authority from local government units to national agencies.

BFAR earlier appealed the trial court's decision but the Supreme Court ruled that the appeal was filed beyond the 15-day deadline, leading to its dismissal and widespread criticism of a 'sluggish defense.'

This decision has serious implications for municipal fishers' preferential rights, local governance, fish stock recovery, and the livelihoods of millions of small-scale fishing families.

FAO 266 – Vessel Monitoring and Electronic Reporting Systems (ERS)

Fisheries Administrative Order 266 (issued October 2020) implements RA 10654's requirement for Vessel Monitoring Measures (VMM) and Electronic Reporting Systems (ERS) for all commercial fishing vessels, creating a national backbone for tracking vessels and catches.

In June 2021, the Malabon Regional Trial Court declared FAO 266 'null and void' following a petition by commercial fishing corporations. The Office of the President suspended implementation nationwide in March 2023, then lifted this suspension in June 2023, directing BFAR to implement FAO 266 except for vessels granted injunctive relief.

The Supreme Court has not yet issued a final decision on consolidated petitions by government, NGOs and fisherfolk. Meanwhile, BFAR reports over 90% of commercial vessels now have monitoring systems installed, but the legal uncertainty has delayed full operationalization of this critical enforcement tool.

VMM/ERS is essential for compliance monitoring, trade obligations, stock assessment data, and combating illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing.

Implementation Challenges

Enforcement of existing laws remains the primary challenge. The scale of the task is daunting: 36,000 kilometers of coastline, 930 coastal local government units (LGUs), over 2.5 million fisherfolk (FishR, 2024), and 88% of assessed stocks showing signs of overfishing. Current response capacity falls far short of what's needed. Most LGUs assign only one fisheries technician for enforcement. BFAR experienced a 28% workforce reduction between 2017 and 2023—losing personnel even as the agency's mandate expanded. While FMAs have established management bodies, many lack harvest control rules and measures, and funding remains insufficient or unclear.

36,000 km
OF COASTLINE

930
COASTAL LGUs

2.5 MILLION+
FISHERFOLK

88% OF ASSESSED STOCKS
SHOW SIGNS OF OVERFISHING

In 2023, there were 353,190 poor fisherfolk families, with 93,030 experiencing food insecurity.

Section 14 of RA 10654 mandates BFAR to establish a coordinated Monitoring, Control, and Surveillance (MCS) system. This system would integrate vessel monitoring, catch documentation, observer programs, port inspections, and inter-agency coordination. However, full operationalization has been delayed by legal challenges, limited inter-agency coordination, and insufficient resources for comprehensive coverage.

Socioeconomic Conditions

In 2023, there were 353,190 poor fisherfolk families, with 93,030 experiencing food insecurity (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2023). The sector shows an aging workforce with declining youth participation. For two decades, fisherfolk have consistently been either the poorest or second-poorest basic sector in the Philippines, indicating persistent structural challenges that require comprehensive intervention.

Assessment Framework

This report examines five interconnected areas:

- Sustainability and Fisheries Management: Stock status and recovery interventions
- Enforcement and Compliance: Law implementation effectiveness
- Institutional Framework: BFAR capacity and performance
- Local Government Implementation: LGU management capabilities
- Socioeconomic Impact: Fisherfolk welfare

The analysis covers the period from 2017 to present using government data, independent research, and field studies to assess RA 10654 implementation effectiveness.

CHAPTER 01

INTRODUCTION

Methodology, Scope, and Limitations

Timeline and Rationale

The primary focus of this assessment covers the period from 2017 to present, representing the post-RA 10654 implementation period. The year 2015 serves as the baseline, marking the status at the time of law amendment passage. Historical data extending before 2015 is included where available to demonstrate longer-term trajectories and provide context for current conditions.

Data Sources

This document draws on multiple data sources to provide comprehensive coverage of Philippine fisheries management:

- Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA): Official production and demographic data
- Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources (BFAR): Agency monitoring and compliance data
- Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG): LGU compliance audits

- Department of Budget and Management (DBM) and Commission on Audit (COA): Budget and audit trails
- Independent research: Academic studies, Oceana monitoring, and field assessments
- Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) satellite data: nighttime light detection of fishing vessels via Karagatan Patrol covering January 2017 to June 2024

Limitations

This is a comprehensive but time-limited rapid assessment. There are significant data gaps in fisheries monitoring and assessments; some critical data was not made available by agencies, and some required data have not been captured in government systems. Data inconsistencies exist across different agencies measuring the same indicators. Where data limitations affect findings, these are noted in the relevant sections.

CHAPTER 02

PRODUCTION TRENDS AND STOCK STATUS

2.1 Overall Production Patterns

Total Fisheries Production (2010-2023, PSA)

Philippine total fisheries production decreased from 2010 to 2016, then stabilized at approximately 4.2-4.4 million metric tons annually through 2023. Current composition

shows aquaculture contributing 52%, municipal capture fisheries 26.1%, and commercial capture fisheries 21.9%.

A notable pattern emerges when examining volume versus value: production volume shows declining trends while economic value continues to increase. This suggests Filipinos are paying more for less fish, indicating both scarcity effects and inflation in the fisheries sector.

Volume of Fisheries Production by Sector (2010-2023)

Volume Share of Total Fisheries Production by Sector (2010-2023)

Value of Fisheries Production by Sector (2010-2023)

Value Share of Total Fisheries Production by Sector (2010-2023)

2.2 Capture Fisheries Decline

Quantified Production Loss

Capture fisheries production decreased from 2.6 million metric tons in 2010 to 1.9 million metric tons in 2023. This represents:

- Total loss over 13 years: 591,136 metric tons of fish
- Average annual loss: 45,472 metric tons
- Trend strength: Very strong decline confirmed by scientific analysis ($R^2 = 0.8984$)

To contextualize this decline: 45,472,000 kilograms of fish are being lost annually—a significant amount that could provide substantial protein requirements to millions of Filipinos.

591,136 mt

13-YR CUMULATIVE LOSS

45,472 mt

AVERAGE ANNUAL LOSS

45,472,000 kg

FISH LOST ANNUALLY

2.3 Stock Assessment Status

National Stock Assessment Program Findings

Based on the most recently published National Stock Assessment Program (NSAP) data (2017), approximately 88% of assessed stocks have exploitation rates exceeding sustainable thresholds, indicating overexploitation and high fishing pressure. Comprehensive national data, however, remains incomplete.

Nevertheless, the management approach must shift from preventing overfishing to actively rebuilding depleted stocks. The data indicates that intensive targeted recovery interventions must be in place, not preventive measures alone.

Volume of Trade of Fish and Fisheries Products (2013-2022)

Value of Trade of Fish and Fisheries Products (2013-2022)

Volume (mt) of Imported Commodities (2022)

Top 10 Sources of Imports by Volume

Volume (mt) of Exported Commodities (2022)

Top 10 Destinations of Exports by Volume

Trade Balance Implications

Historically, the Philippines maintained positive fisheries trade balance with export value consistently exceeding imports. By 2022, this difference had narrowed to only US\$292,250.

A fisherman is shown in the foreground, holding a large fish. The background is filled with numerous fishing boats docked in a harbor. The entire image has a blue color overlay.

CHAPTER 03

**MANAGEMENT
INTERVENTIONS
AND
EFFECTIVENESS**

AUDIT QUESTION

Are fisheries management interventions (FMAs, closed seasons, harvest controls, and MPAs) being implemented effectively? Are they producing measurable results in fish stock health?

BASELINE

RA 10654 (2015) mandates science-based fisheries management. In 2019, FAO 263 was issued, establishing 12 FMAs.

The Fisheries Code requires 15% of coastal areas as fish sanctuaries.

THE FINDING

The current governance framework shows genuine progress. As of 2023, all 12 Fisheries Management Areas have functioning management bodies. Half have approved management plans. Four FMAs score “excellent” on process indicators, reflecting strong stakeholder participation and planning capacity.

And yet, this institutional progress has not translated to ecological recovery. The marine ecosystem remains in crisis. Approximately 88% of assessed fish stocks sit in the “red zone”—overfished or overexploited. A recent nationwide stock assessment has been completed, but the government has yet to make the data publicly available.

Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) exist on paper but many lack effective enforcement. Closed fishing seasons have produced some localized recovery in a few areas but these seasonal closures alone cannot reverse the decline. They need to work alongside comprehensive effort controls such as limits on the total number of boats, restrictions on fishing gear, and protection of critical habitats like spawning grounds.

Technical terms used in FMA management include: **Reference Points** (scientific benchmarks indicating stock health status), **HCRs** (pre-agreed management actions triggered when stocks reach certain reference points), and **Ecosystem Approach to Fisheries Management (EAFM)**, which considers the entire ecosystem rather than focusing solely on target species.

While management tools already exist, their full use and execution leaves much to be desired. Harvest Control Rules (HCR) provide science-based guidelines for how much fish can be safely extracted. Species-specific management plans have been drafted for major commercial stocks. Monitoring frameworks exist to track compliance and catch data. Unfortunately, the application and implementation of these plans remain fragmented, with some regions enforcing rules while others treat them as mere suggestions. Moreover, funding falls short of what is needed for consistent patrols and monitoring. The critical gap persists: all these governance activities (meetings, plans, frameworks) have yet to produce measurable improvements in stock health at a meaningful scale.

3.1 Fisheries Management Areas (FMAs)

Design and Intent

FMAs were established four years after RA 10654 was enacted. Fisheries Administrative Order (FAO) 263, issued in 2019 set the guidelines dividing Philippine waters into 12 FMAs based on fisheries ecosystem, rather than political boundaries.

The FMA approach incorporates three key features:

1. **Decentralized Management:** Management Boards include representatives from national government, LGUs, academe, civil society, and fishing sectors
2. **Science-Based Approach:** Stock assessments, Reference Points,

and Harvest Control Rules guide management decisions

3. **Co-Management:** BFAR, LGUs, and stakeholders work together following Ecosystem Approach to Fisheries Management (EAFM) principles

3.2 FMA Implementation Status

Process Achievements

As of the most recent reporting period (2023), FMA implementation shows the following progress:

1. All 12 FMAs have established management bodies
2. All have scientific advisory groups and technical working groups
3. 50% have adopted and approved FMA Management Plans
4. 33% have approved reference points and formulated Harvest Control Rules to guide fishing limits
5. 42% have established Monitoring and Evaluation Action Plans to track progress

By 2022, all FMAs were rated 'Good' or 'Excellent' based on FAO 263 compliance indicators. Four FMAs (FMA 1, 7, 11, 12) showed excellent performance. The FMA Scorecard results are summarized below.

Implementation Challenges

Several critical challenges persist despite progress in some aspects of the FMA implementation. Research by Ferrer et al. (2024) identified three main issues:

1. Limited funding
2. Weak representation of municipal fishers, with often only one representative for the entire municipal sector
3. Inconsistent level of FMA implementation in different parts of the country due to unclear operational rules and implementation timelines

The FMA Scorecard effectively measures governance processes and represents important progress. However, there remains a critical need to connect these governance indicators with actual stock status outcomes. Despite 'excellent' scores on process indicators such as meetings held, plans written, and committees formed, the translation of this promising governance framework to measurable ecological outcomes has not yet been demonstrated.

Fisheries Management (FMA) Scorecard Rollout Summary

	2020	2022		2020	2022		2020	2022
FMA 1	4	35	FMA 5	4	32	FMA 9	9	22
FMA 2	10	22	FMA 6	6	32	FMA 10	5	24
FMA 3	4	26	FMA 7	11	33	FMA 11	4	35
FMA 4	4	N/A	FMA 8	10	29	FMA 12	4	35

3.3 National Management Plans

BFAR has completed and approved several species-specific management plans:

- National Tuna Management Plan (2018; approved)
- National Sardine Management Plan (2020; approved)
- Blue Swimming Crab National Management Plan (2022; approved)
- Octopus National Management Framework Plan (2021; drafted)

The implementation status of these plans varies across species and regions. Comprehensive monitoring of implementation effectiveness and outcomes remains a need.

3.4 Closed Fishing Seasons

Current Implementation

Various closed seasons have been established for different species and areas including:

- Sardines in FMA 4 (Zamboanga Peninsula and Sulu Archipelago) in 2011
- Roundscads or galunggong in FMA 5 (Northern Palawan) in 2015, and
- Common small pelagic stocks in FMA 2 (Davao Gulf starting 2014), FMA 11 (Visayan Sea starting 2013), and FMA 12 (Balayan Bay starting 2014)

Some evidence suggests localized stock recovery in areas such as Davao Gulf and Zamboanga Peninsula. However, scientific data shows many fish populations remain overfished even after years of seasonal closures.

Assessment of closed seasons indicates they are insufficient by themselves for stock recovery.

Comprehensive measures are needed including:

- Limiting overall fishing effort beyond seasonal restrictions
- Protecting critical habitats
- Providing alternative livelihood support
- Ensuring strong community engagement and enforcement

Success depends on fisher understanding and support, combined with robust government-community cooperation in implementation and enforcement.

3.5 Harvest Control Rules (HCR) and Harvest Control Measures (HCM)

Purpose and Function

Across FMAs, HCRs and HCMs are designed to guide and limit fish extraction based on stock health indicators, fishing pressure metrics, and population trend analysis.

A data transparency challenge exists: there is no updated, publicly accessible consolidated national database of stock status. Based on the most recent available publication, approximately 88% of assessed fish stocks are in what is characterized as the 'red zone'—indicating they are overfished, overexploited, or unable to replenish adequately.

HCRs and HCMs serve important functions: these set limits when populations decline, adjust harvest levels based on current stock status, provide fish populations opportunity to recover, and help sustain resources that communities depend on for their food and livelihoods. The goal is not to stop fishing entirely but to ensure fishing can continue sustainably in the future through stronger rules, better monitoring, and transparent reporting of stock status.

Status of fisheries stocks in the 12 FMAs (NSAP, 2017)

	Total no. species monitored	Total no. stocks overfished	% overfished stocks		Total no. species monitored	Total no. stocks overfished	% overfished stocks
FMA 1	24	20	83.3	FMA 7	21	18	85.7
FMA 2	9	8	88.9	FMA 8	11	9	81.8
FMA 3	24	19	79.2	FMA 9	6	6	100
FMA 4	6	4	66.7	FMA 10	8	8	100
FMA 5	9	7	77.8	FMA 11	16	16	100
FMA 6	17	17	100	FMA 12	15	15	100

3.6 Marine Protected Areas (MPAs)

Legal Requirement and Current Status

The Philippine Fisheries Code mandates that at least 15% of total coastal areas in each municipality shall be designated as fish sanctuaries. As of 2023, 2,112 MPAs have been established, mostly at the barangay-LGU level. The modal size category is 10-100 hectares.

The Implementation Gap

A 2007 estimate indicated that less than 10% of MPAs showed effective management with properly enforced no-take zones, with most are existing as 'paper' MPAs with minimal actual implementation. While no comprehensive updated effectiveness estimate is available in recent reports, and Management Effectiveness Assessment Tools (MEAT) have likely improved some MPAs, research suggests a high proportion of paper MPAs persists.

Less than 10% of MPAs showed effective management with properly enforced no-take zones

Research evidence shows MPAs can be effective when properly managed. Well-managed MPAs have been shown to improve coral cover, increase the diversity and density of commercially important reef fish, and generate positive spillover effects that enhance fishing productivity in adjacent areas.

However, research also identifies factors limiting MPA effectiveness:

- Poor enforcement capacity
- Limited financial and technical resources
- Pressures from adjacent fishing activities
- Management weaknesses including unclear zoning and inadequate surveillance
- Short-term fisher income losses not adequately addressed
- Benefits not equitably distributed among stakeholders

Equity and Governance Considerations

Studies have identified important equity and governance issues in MPA management. Key factors leading to MPA success include community participation, their understanding of the crisis in resources, and the availability of alternative livelihoods. Women, particularly those dependent on intertidal gleaning, may be disproportionately affected by MPA regulations yet remain underrepresented in governance processes.

In general, MPAs have contributed substantially to biodiversity conservation and local fisheries management in the Philippines. However, overall effectiveness is limited by small size, fragmented planning, inconsistent enforcement, and governance challenges. What is needed includes: scaling up local and smaller MPAs into ecologically coherent networks, integrating MPAs into broader marine spatial planning

frameworks, and addressing social equity in both benefits and decision-making processes. Decision-making processes must involve the communities who rely on these waters—particularly small-scale fishers who have the most at stake.

These steps are necessary for enhancing both ecological resilience and social equity in fisheries management. When done right, this approach can create social equity in two ways: as it distributes benefits more fairly through networked MPAs with spillover effects, it also ensures genuine and inclusive representation. When fisherfolk participate meaningfully in planning and enforcement, they gain from the agency's management of resources that determine their livelihoods. This combination of ecological coherence and genuine community participation builds both resilience in marine ecosystems and fairness in how fishing opportunities and management responsibilities are shared.

RESULT

BFAR has achieved structural progress through FMAs established, policies issued, and seasonal closures implemented. This agency is doing its best with its current resources, but lacks the workforce, budget allocation, and coordination mechanisms needed to be effective in performing its mandated functions. A 28% personnel loss combined with 68% contractual workforce limits institutional capacity. Performance metrics may reward process compliance while ecological outcomes continue to deteriorate. Effectiveness depends on reversing workforce decline, ensuring adequate budget allocation, and establishing the coordinated MCS system mandated by law.

A blue-tinted photograph showing a person's hands and arms as they handle a large quantity of fish, likely salmon, in a processing facility. The fish are piled up, and a long wooden pole is visible, possibly used for sorting or moving the fish. The overall scene is dimly lit, with the blue tint dominating the color palette.

CHAPTER 04

**ENFORCEMENT
& COMPLIANCE**

AUDIT QUESTION

Are fisheries laws being enforced effectively? Are vessels being monitored effectively? Is illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing being addressed and prevented?

BASELINE

RA 10654 (2015) mandates vessel monitoring (VMM), fisher registration, and protection of municipal waters (0-15km). FAO 266 (2020) details implementation.

THE FINDING

From January 2017 to June 2024, satellite monitoring detected 270,165 lights from apparent illegal fishing activity in municipal waters meant to be protected for small-scale fishers. The full implementation of VMM was stalled when the commercial fishing sector filed a case, and then the Office of the President issued a suspension order. The suspension was eventually lifted and the BFAR now claims over 90% implementation. However, BFAR is still not sharing the data from VMM/Vessel Monitoring Measures on the fish catch data and actual apprehension and prosecution of violators. Registration systems produce conflicting counts of fishers and vessels. Nine years after RA 10654's passage, enforcement gaps persist at every governance level.

4.1 Registration Systems: Two Databases, Two Different Counts

WHAT WE AUDITED: Consistency and accuracy of fisherfolk and vessel registration systems (For fisherfolk registration: PSA 2022, FishR 2022).

OUR FINDINGS: The 2022 PSA Census counted 853,065 fishing operators. BFAR's Municipal

Fisherfolk Registration (FishR) system recorded 1,173,381 registered fishers in 2022. These are not minor statistical variations but discrepancies large enough to undermine program targeting, resource allocation, and policy planning.

The largest gaps appear in regions with the highest fishing pressure: Region IV-A (53,393 difference), Region III (46,675), and BARMM (43,588). In these areas, where fishing pressure is intense and coastal populations are large, accurate fisher counts are not administrative niceties but essential for determining how many livelihoods will be affected by management decisions and what government investments are needed to support displaced fishers.

Commercial fleet registration. Registered commercial vessels declined approximately 40% between 2018 and 2023. The decline may be due to the exit of these vessels from fishery or there may be gaps in registration, monitoring and tracking of vessels.

Field studies reveal the extent of unregistered commercial operations. In the Visayan Sea, BFAR records showed 5 registered trawlers in 2017; actual field counts exceeded 300 vessels. For FMA 11, BFAR listed 57 sensuro (round-haul seine) vessels in 2022-23, yet one independent study documented 31-35 sensuro vessels in Concepcion, Iloilo alone—a single municipality within the FMA.

OUR ASSESSMENT: You cannot manage what you cannot count. Policy decisions are being made on unreliable data and resources are being allocated to populations whose actual size is unknown. When vessels remain unregistered and unregulated, enforcement becomes fragmented and ineffective, creating conditions for IUU fishing. Enforcement targets vessels that may or may not appear in official registries. All these contribute to enforcement that is weak and could be significantly improved.

4.2 Vessel Monitoring: Three Years Without Oversight

WHAT WE AUDITED: Implementation status of VMM and electronic reporting systems mandated by RA 10654.

OUR FINDINGS: Five years after RA 10654's passage, FAO 266 was issued in 2020 to implement vessel monitoring. Before the system became operational, the Malabon Regional Trial Court suspended the order. Since 2021, every commercial fishing vessel in Philippine waters has operated without meaningful and effective monitoring. This has contributed to three years of unchecked operations, and unverified catch reports.

This extends a longer pattern of data neglect. Commercial vessel catch data has been legally required since the 1998 Fisheries Code—26 years of mandatory reporting. BFAR has not fully utilized the system despite about 90% of commercial vessels installed with VMM devices as of 2024. Catch documentation, which involves daily fishing log sheets detailing catch volume, species, and fishing grounds, is not publicly available and effectively used for management purposes. Ideally, this historical catch data could have provided indices of stock abundance, documented the timeline of fisheries deterioration, and prompted earlier intervention when recovery prospects were more favorable.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Without vessel monitoring, there is little we can do to verify accurately where commercial vessels fish, what they catch, or whether they comply with regulations. Invalidating VMM removes accountability

from the commercial sector and makes the Philippines non-compliant with international commitments to ensure better transparency in fisheries and to address illegal fishing.

4.3 Municipal Waters: 270,165 Detected Intrusions

WHAT WE AUDITED: Protection of municipal waters (0-15km from shore) designated for preferential use of municipal fisherfolk under RA 10654.

OUR FINDINGS: Satellite data from Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) reveal night lights emanating supposedly from commercial fishing vessels inside municipal waters. The detections of 270,165 from January 2017 to January 2024 were collected and analyzed by Karagatan Patrol. These detections—which represent incidents of light over approximately 25 hectares of water—serve as reliable indicators for apparent commercial vessel presence in municipal waters and protected areas.

The highest apparent intrusion rates concentrate in specific areas:

1. Zamboanga City (FMA 4): 185.7 detections per month
2. Tongkil (FMA 4): 153.4 detections per month
3. Languyan (FMA 4): 77.6 detections per month

FMA 4 (East Sulu Sea/Moro Gulf), 5 (Northern Palawan), and 11 (Visayan Sea) each place four municipalities in the top 20 for intrusions, making them clear enforcement priority zones.

Municipal fishers earning Php 2,500-7,000 per month who are already the poorest or second-poorest basic sector in the country.

The 10.1-15 kilometer authorization gap.

Of the 930 coastal LGUs, 174 authorize commercial fishing in the 10.1-15 kilometer zone. Section 18 of RA 10654 permits this only when specific conditions are met: waters must exceed 7 fathoms depth (requiring NAMRIA certification), fishing methods must comply with national policies, public hearings with Fisheries and Aquatic Resources Management Councils (FARMCs) must occur, and vessels must have clean violation records. Commercial fishing in bays in an environmentally critical condition and during closed season is absolutely prohibited.

Of the 174 LGUs authorizing commercial fishing, apparently only one has obtained the required National Mapping and Resource Information Authority (NAMRIA) depth certification. Other Section 18 requirements—method approval, FARMC consultation, violation checks—are similarly weakly enforced or ignored. In Region IV-B, over 50% of LGUs authorize commercial access to these waters.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Municipal waters were designated for small-scale fishers precisely because they are already the poorest sector. They cannot compete with commercial fishing that catches more fish stocks meant to be protected, and unduly destroys important marine habitats. These further deplete the resource base of municipal fishers who depend on these for their survival. 2021 data from the IUU Fishing Index and Threat Assessment (I-FIT) tool indicate a moderate risk of national IUUF, with several FMAs showing high risk scores.

Only 1 out of 174 LGUs complied with the conditions to allow commercial fishing inside the 10.1-15km zone

4.4 The Economic Cost: Php 5.4 Billion Lost Annually

Illegal, unreported, and unregulated (IUU) fishing cost the Philippines an estimated ₱5.4 billion from 2022 to 2023. This represents economic value stolen from the sector—municipal fishers earning ₱2,500-7,000 per month who are already the poorest or second-poorest basic sector in the country.

Fine mesh nets—which capture juvenile fish before reproduction, destroying future productivity—were reported in 74% of LGUs. Despite widespread use of this destructive gear, enforcement remains sporadic and penalties insufficient to change behavior.

Based on the I-FIT tool, the Philippines improved its IUU risk score from 2.58 in 2021 to 2.36 in 2023, indicating better assessment capacity. However, improved measurement without effective enforcement simply provides clearer documentation of ongoing resource extraction.

4.5 Enforcement and Compliance: Audit Summary

RESULT:

Enforcement systems are weak, and registration data is unreliable

The full implementation of VMM has been stalled when the commercial fishing sector filed a case, followed by a suspension order from the Office of the President. Although this suspension was eventually lifted and the BFAR now claims over 90% implementation, there is no data sharing on the actual performance and effectiveness of the VMM/VMS in tracking

vessels, getting fish catch data and actual apprehension and prosecution of violators. Municipal waters show 270,165 apparent intrusion incidents over seven years. While RA 10654 provides a robust legal framework, implementation failures at every level leave the law without teeth.

CHAPTER 05

INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY - BEAR PERFORMANCE

CV FEB-102319-22429

AUDIT QUESTION

Does BFAR have the capacity to implement RA 10654? Are resources adequate for the mandate?

BASELINE

BFAR is responsible for 36,354 km coastline, 930 coastal LGUs, 2.5M+ fisherfolk, and 12 FMAs. RA 10654 expanded mandates significantly in 2015.

THE FINDING

BFAR lost 1,938 personnel (28% of its workforce) between 2017 and 2023 while mandates expanded. The agency achieves process compliance metrics while capture fisheries production declines by 45,472 metric tons annually. Commission on Audit reports document recurring failures to deploy allocated budgets. Policy production is high; implementation capacity is insufficient.

5.1 The Workforce Decline: 28% Personnel Loss

WHAT WE AUDITED: BFAR staffing levels and workforce composition from 2017 to 2023.

OUR FINDINGS: BFAR's personnel decreased from 6,925 in 2017 to 4,987 in 2023—a loss of 1,938 people (28%). The remaining workforce is 68% contractual, meaning non-permanent positions that limit institutional memory, career development, and long-term capacity building.

While the Department of Agriculture's budget increased from ₱39.24 billion in 2010 to ₱124.44 billion in 2025, BFAR received only 6-15% of this allocation. The workforce decline in BFAR occurred unfortunately at a time when RA 10654 expanded BFAR's responsibilities: establishing 12 FMAs,

implementing vessel monitoring, strengthening LGU technical support, enhancing enforcement coordination, and managing ecosystem-based approaches across the entire coastline.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Each person lost represents dozens of fishing communities without adequate technical support, hundreds of vessels without monitoring, and thousands of hectares without management attention. You cannot expand mandates while shrinking the workforce responsible for implementation.

5.2 Meeting Metrics While Fisheries Collapse

WHAT WE AUDITED: BFAR's performance ratings against official targets and ecological outcomes.

OUR FINDINGS: BFAR consistently achieves approximately 75 Performance-Based Bonus (PBB) points, meeting official performance metrics. Simultaneously, capture fisheries production continues declining by 45,472 metric tons annually. The performance measurement system rewards administrative compliance—meetings held, reports submitted, plans approved—rather than ecological outcomes like fish stock recovery or reduced overfishing.

Achievement rates for Congress-approved targets range from 66-77%. Over time, this institutionalizes underperformance: a 70% success rate becomes the accepted norm rather than a signal that implementation capacity is insufficient.

OUR ASSESSMENT: An institution can report success on paper while presiding over resource collapse in reality. Performance systems that measure process instead of outcomes create perverse incentives where checking boxes becomes more important than achieving conservation goals.

5.3 Policy Volume Without Implementation Capacity

WHAT WE AUDITED: Fisheries Administrative Orders (FAOs) issued since 2015 and their implementation status.

OUR FINDINGS: BFAR has issued 31 Fisheries Administrative Orders since RA 10654's passage—one every 3.5 months. This demonstrates technical capacity and responsiveness. However, key orders remain stalled (pending case questioning FAO 266 on vessel monitoring), weakly enforced (Section 18 requirements for commercial fishing), or implemented without adequate resources for effective compliance monitoring.

Each policy order requires implementation capacity: personnel to administer it, monitoring systems to track compliance, enforcement mechanisms to address violations, and budget allocations to support operations. Without corresponding increases in these resources, high policy production can paradoxically weaken overall effectiveness by spreading limited capacity across too many initiatives.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Policies on paper are not policies in practice. The gap between regulatory ambition and implementation capacity grows with each new order issued without corresponding resource allocation.

5.4 Commission on Audit Findings: A Pattern of Dysfunction

WHAT WE AUDITED: Commission on Audit (COA) reports on BFAR from 2016 to 2023.

OUR FINDINGS: COA reports document recurring failures year after year:

1. Unutilized funds: budgets allocated but not deployed to programs
2. Delayed distribution: programs reaching beneficiaries months or years behind schedule
3. Inadequate monitoring: inability to track program outcomes or beneficiary impacts
4. Gender budgets unused: funds allocated for women-specific programs remain unspent
5. Livelihood programs delayed: support reaches fisherfolk too late or not at all

These are not one-time implementation problems, but systemic patterns appearing in audit after audit. They indicate institutional paralysis in translating appropriations into effective action.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Livelihood programs are delayed or unutilized while fisherfolk poverty rates increase. Gender budgets sit unused while women in fisheries remain underserved. Unutilized funds represent missed opportunities to support the sector during years of continued stock decline. Administrative dysfunction has direct human cost.

5.5 The Monitoring System and Its Requirements

WHAT WE AUDITED: Implementation of the coordinated Monitoring, Control, and Surveillance (MCS) system mandated by RA 10654 Section 14.

OUR FINDINGS: Section 14 mandates BFAR to establish an MCS system “in coordination with LGUs, FARMCs, the private sector and other agencies concerned.” This coordinated system has not been established. Enforcement remains fragmented: BFAR operates independently of LGUs, separately from the Philippine Coast Guard, and autonomously of the Philippine National Police.

Without integrated infrastructure, violations fall through jurisdictional gaps. A commercial vessel caught by an LGU may be outside that LGU’s penalty authority. BFAR may lack information about local enforcement activities. The Philippine Coast Guard may interdict vessels but lacks support for prosecution. Information doesn’t flow between agencies, and coordination remains ad hoc rather than systematic.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Fragmented enforcement is weak enforcement. Despite BFAR’s best efforts, without coordination, even dedicated individual agencies cannot achieve the systematic compliance needed for fisheries recovery.

This agency is doing its best with its current resources, but lacks the workforce, budget allocation, and coordination mechanisms

5.6 BFAR Performance: Audit Summary

RESULTS:

BFAR has achieved structural progress through FMAs established, policies issued, and seasonal closures implemented.

needed to be effective in performing its mandated functions. A 28% personnel loss combined with 68% contractual workforce limits institutional capacity. Performance metrics reward process compliance while ecological outcomes deteriorate. Effectiveness depends on reversing workforce decline, ensuring adequate budget allocation, and establishing the coordinated MCS system mandated by law.

CHAPTER 06

LOCAL GOVERNMENT IMPLEMENTATION

AUDIT QUESTION

Are LGUs implementing fisheries management effectively? Do they have adequate capacity, authority, and resources?

BASELINE

930 coastal LGUs manage municipal waters (0-15km). RA 10654 assigns them responsibility for enforcement, FARMCs, CRM plans, and Bantay Dagat operations.

THE FINDING

Only about half of coastal LGUs have updated their fisheries ordinances since RA 10654. LGUs can fine violators a maximum of ₱2,500 for municipalities and ₱3,000 for cities while RA 10654 allows up to ₱5 million—authority inadequate to the responsibility. Only 51% have delineated municipal waters, making enforcement of boundaries nearly impossible. Bantay Dagat units operate at one-third of the recommended budget. Many LGUs are trying to manage fisheries in their jurisdictions, but most lack the tools to succeed.

6.1 Outdated Legal Frameworks

WHAT WE AUDITED: LGU fisheries ordinance adoption and updating status since RA 10654 (2015).

OUR FINDINGS: According to the DILG 2023 Fisheries Compliance Audit Report, approximately 54% of coastal LGUs have ordinances addressing IUU fishing—meaning about half have updated their legal frameworks since RA 10654. Approximately 8% of coastal LGUs have yet to enact any fisheries ordinance at all.

Ten years after the amended Fisheries Code became law, 46% of coastal LGUs are still operating with pre-2015 regulations. They

lack the enhanced provisions on vessel monitoring, stricter penalties, ecosystem-based management, and municipal water protections that RA 10654 introduced.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Local ordinances are the primary legal tool for municipal water management. Without updated ordinances reflecting RA 10654, LGUs cannot implement the law's key provisions locally. Enforcement efforts operate under outdated legal frameworks that may conflict with national policy.

6.2 The Penalty Authority Gap

WHAT WE AUDITED: LGU authority to impose penalties for fisheries violations.

OUR FINDINGS: RA 7160 (Local Government Code) limits LGU fines to a maximum of ₱2,500 for municipalities and ₱3,000 for cities. RA 10654 provides for penalties ranging from ₱10,000 to ₱5,000,000 for various violations—but these can only be imposed by the DA-BFAR Adjudication Committee, not by LGUs.

LGUs are assigned responsibility for managing and protecting municipal waters. They are held accountable for enforcement of rules in their municipal waters. Yet they have limited penalizing authority to make violations costly enough to deter repeat offenders. For instance, a commercial vessel caught fishing illegally in municipal waters can be fined ₱2,500 by the municipality and/or ₱3,000 by the city government— amounts unlikely to change behavior when a single fishing trip generates far more revenues for offenders.

OUR ASSESSMENT: The prevalence of illegal fishing in municipal waters and continued commercial vessel encroachment suggests that available penalties are not deterring violations.

LGUs are assigned responsibility for managing and protecting municipal waters.

LGUs have the responsibility, which however, is not matched with the commensurate authority to be able to enforce the rules effectively.

6.3 The Boundaries That Don't Exist

WHAT WE AUDITED: Municipal water delineation status across coastal LGUs.

OUR FINDINGS: Only 51% of coastal LGUs have officially delineated their municipal waters. The remaining 49% lack clearly defined boundaries on official maps. Regional variation is significant: Region V has delineated 75% of municipal waters, while Region II has delineated only 22%.

Without clear boundaries, enforcement becomes nearly impossible. How do you stop a commercial vessel from entering municipal waters when those waters are not precisely defined? How do you prosecute boundary violations when the boundary itself is ambiguous? How do you explain to a fisher where they can and cannot operate?

OUR ASSESSMENT: Undefined boundaries create enforcement paralysis, enable jurisdictional disputes, and allow commercial vessels to exploit ambiguity. Fisher rights vary by geography—not based on law but based on whether an LGU has completed the delineation process.

6.4 Commercial Access to Municipal Waters

WHAT WE AUDITED: LGU compliance with RA 10654 Section 18 requirements for authorizing commercial fishing in the 10.1-15km zone.

OUR FINDINGS: Of the 930 coastal LGUs, 174 authorize commercial fishing in the 10.1-15 kilometer zone of municipal waters. Section 18 permits this authorization only when all of the following conditions are met: (1) waters are 7 fathoms or more in depth as certified by NAMRIA, (2) fishing methods are consistent with national policies, (3) public hearings with Municipal/City FARMCs have been conducted, and (4) vessels, owners, employers, captains, and crew have no violation records. Commercial fishing in bays in an environmentally critical condition and during closed season is absolutely prohibited.

Of the 174 LGUs authorizing commercial fishing, apparently only one has complied with the NAMRIA depth certification requirement. Other Section 18 requirements appear similarly weakly enforced. In Region IV-B, over 50% of LGUs authorize commercial access.

OUR ASSESSMENT: The 10.1-15km zone was designated as a buffer where commercial access requires strict conditions precisely because municipal fishers need protection from commercial competition. When these conditions are ignored, the protection disappears and commercial pressure on municipal stocks continues unchecked.

6.5 Community Governance: FARMCs on Paper

WHAT WE AUDITED: Establishment and functionality of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources Management Councils (FARMCs).

OUR FINDINGS: Approximately 94% of coastal LGUs report having created FARMCs, suggesting widespread adoption of community-based governance. However, research studies indicate many FARMCs are inactive, underfunded, or fail to encourage meaningful fisherfolk participation. In BARMM, only 28 of 73 LGUs report having FARMCs at all.

The gap between formal establishment and functional effectiveness is significant. A FARMC that exists on paper but holds no meetings, has no budget, and makes no decisions is a FARMC in name only. Community-based governance was mandated, but the resources and support systems to make it functional were not adequately provided.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Effective fisheries management requires community participation. When FARMCs are non-functional, local ecological knowledge goes unused; community support for regulations weakens, and enforcement becomes purely top-down rather than locally owned.

6.6 Plans Without Implementation Monitoring

WHAT WE AUDITED: Coastal Resource Management (CRM) plan adoption and implementation status.

OUR FINDINGS: Approximately 71% of coastal LGUs have CRM plans, with most incorporated or mainstreamed into local development plans. However, critical implementation questions remain unanswered: Are LGUs meeting the 10% aquaculture area requirement? Are they achieving the 15% MPA allocation mandated by RA 10654? Were communities actually involved in planning processes? Is anyone systematically monitoring plan implementation and achievement of objectives?

OUR ASSESSMENT: Plans are starting points, not endpoints. A plan that sits on a shelf while fish stocks continue to decline is not a management tool but a mere documentation of unfulfilled intentions. Without implementation monitoring, there is no accountability for whether plans translate into effective action and consequently into meaningful outcomes.

6.7 Bantay Dagat: Willing But Under-Resourced Enforcers

WHAT WE AUDITED: Bantay Dagat establishment, capacity, and resource adequacy.

OUR FINDINGS: Approximately 78% of coastal LGUs have deputized Bantay Dagat enforcement officers. In BARMM, only 32% have any enforcement capacity at all. The average annual Bantay Dagat budget is ₱400,000 per LGU, while the recommended adequate budget is ₱1.2 million—meaning most units operate at one-third of needed resources. The operational challenges are substantial:

- Not all LGUs have floating assets for seaborne patrols
- Not all can allocate financial resources for regular patrol operations
- Municipal water areas can be vast, making constant surveillance difficult
- Assigned PNP personnel are often inadequate in number
- Equipment is inadequate for enforcement needs
- Safety risks for enforcement officers are significant
- Legal counsel support for prosecutions is limited or absent

Despite Bantay Dagat presence in most LGUs, VIIRS satellite data continues to show apparent illegal fishing activity in municipal waters. This suggests that while enforcement units exist and personnel are willing, resources are insufficient for the scale of enforcement needed.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Municipal water protection depends on local enforcement. When Bantay Dagat units lack boats, fuel, equipment, and legal support, enforcement becomes episodic rather than systematic, and violations continue because the likelihood of consequences is low.

6.8 Local Government Implementation: Audit Summary

RESULT: Many coastal LGUs are attempting to fulfill their fisheries management responsibilities, but systemic constraints prevent effective implementation. Only half have updated ordinances. LGU penalty authority (₱2,500/₱3,000 maximum) is grossly inadequate. Half lack delineated boundaries. Bantay Dagat operates at one-third of the recommended budget. LGUs are being asked to protect 36,000 kilometers of coastline with insufficient legal authority, unclear boundaries, and under-resourced enforcement units. While LGUs have the authority and responsibility, without adequate tools and sufficient resources, it should come as no surprise that violations persist.

SYNTHESIS: ENFORCEMENT WITHOUT CAPACITY

THE CORE PROBLEM: The Philippines has a comprehensive legal framework for fisheries management in RA 10654. What is lacking is the institutional capacity and adequate resources to implement that framework effectively.

At the national level (BFAR):

- 28% workforce loss while mandates expanded
- 68% contractual workforce limits institutional memory

- Performance systems reward process, not outcomes
- High policy production without implementation resources
- Coordinated MCS system not established despite legal mandate

At the local level (LGUs):

- Half lack updated ordinances reflecting RA 10654
- Penalty authority inadequate (₱2,500/₱3,000 max vs. ₱5M available penalties)
- 49% lack delineated municipal water boundaries
- Bantay Dagat operates at one-third recommended budget
- Section 18 compliance for commercial fishing within 10.1-15km nearly absent

In enforcement infrastructure:

- Registration systems produce conflicting data (320,318 fisher discrepancy)
- Vessel monitoring suspended for three years
- 270,165 apparent intrusion detections in municipal waters
- ₱5.4 billion lost to IUU fishing annually

STATUS QUO: We can detect apparent violations via satellite. We know where apparent illegal fishing occurs. We have laws penalizing illegal activities. What we lack is the workforce to respond, the budget to sustain enforcement, the coordination mechanisms to connect agencies, the penalty authority at the local level to make violations costly, and the monitoring systems to create accountability.

BFAR produces policies while they lose personnel required to implement them effectively. LGUs are assigned responsibility without sufficient authority. Bantay Dagat units patrol and operate with only one-third of the needed budget. Full implementation of vessel monitoring is stalled by a pending case in the Supreme Court. Registration systems cannot agree on how many fishers exist. Commercial vessels fish in municipal waters, and while detection systems document these intrusions, enforcement remains episodic.

What does this imply?

Until implementation capacity matches the policy ambition, Philippine fisheries management will continue to experience decline rather than achieve recovery. The legal framework exists. What remains absent is the political will and the institutional infrastructure i.e., personnel, budget, coordination, authority, and accountability systems, needed to translate law into practice and practice into envisioned ecological outcomes.

CHAPTER 07

**SOCIOECONOMIC
STATUS OF
FISHERFOLK**

In 10-15 years, there may be insufficient fishers to maintain current production levels, regardless of stock status.

AUDIT QUESTION

What is the socioeconomic status of fisherfolk? How are current government programs improving their welfare?

BASELINE

The Philippines has 2.5M+ fisherfolk. RA 10654 emphasizes fisherfolk welfare. Multiple livelihood programs have been implemented since 2015.

THE FINDING

For two decades, fisherfolk have been the poorest or second-poorest basic sector in the Philippines. In 2023, 353,190 fisherfolk families live in poverty; 93,030 experience food insecurity. The sector is aging, with mean age of 49-52 years, and youth refusing to enter the fishing industry. Despite substantial government programs distributing boats, gear, and training, poverty incidence remains at 27.4% compared to a 15.5% national average. The data indicates that while efforts are being made, current interventions have not yet achieved the transformation needed to break the poverty cycle.

7.1 Demographics: Who Are the Fisherfolk?

WHAT WE AUDITED: Demographic characteristics of the fishing population, including age distribution and registration accuracy.

Registration discrepancies. The 2022 PSA Census counted 853,065 fishing operators. The 2024 FishR system recorded 1,173,381—a difference of 320,318 people. The largest gaps appear in regions with high fishing pressure: Region IV-A (53,393), Region III (46,675), and BARMM (43,588). This discrepancy complicates targeting of support programs and resource allocation decisions. It would be ideal to harmonize the two databases (PSA & FishR) to align and maximize efforts.

An aging workforce. Between 2012 and 2022, the number of fishers under age 50 decreased by 3.6%, while those aged 50 and over increased by 36.4%. In 2012, 73% of fishers were aged 50 or younger; by 2022, this had declined to 55%. Current mean age ranges from 49-52 years across studies.

Young people are declining to enter fishing, citing low income, limited advancement opportunities, physical demands and risks, and instability. This demographic shift threatens not only the sector's future workforce but also the intergenerational transfer of ecological knowledge essential for community-based management.

OUR ASSESSMENT: An aging workforce without youth replacement suggests the sector's economic conditions are not attractive enough to sustain generational continuity. In 10-15 years, there may be insufficient fishers to maintain current production levels, regardless of stock status.

7.2 Economic Status: Two Decades of Persistent Poverty

WHAT WE AUDITED: Poverty incidence, income levels, and food security among fisherfolk from 2003-2023.

Poverty status. In 2023, fisherfolk poverty incidence was 27.4%—significantly above the national average of 15.5%. Historically, fisherfolk were the poorest basic sector from 2003-2015 and in 2021, and the second poorest in 2018 and 2023. This twenty-year pattern indicates structural poverty, not temporary hardship.

While poverty incidence percentages have shown slight improvement in some years, the absolute number of poor fisherfolk has increased: from 287,070 in 2018 to 342,760 in 2021 to 353,190 in 2023. Population growth is outpacing poverty reduction, meaning more fisherfolk families are poor today than five years ago despite programs and interventions.

Food insecurity among food producers.

While 353,190 fisherfolk families fall below the national poverty line in 2023 (meaning they cannot meet basic food and non-food needs), 93,030 of these families are considered food-poor—a subset unable to afford even the minimum daily food requirements. This represents 7.2% of fisherfolk living below the food poverty threshold. The distinction is critical: poverty incidence measures those who cannot afford basic necessities (food plus non-food items like shelter, clothing, education), while food poverty specifically measures those who cannot adequately feed themselves despite producing food for the nation. Subsistence incidence among fisherfolk consistently exceeds that of most other basic sectors.

Regional concentration shows BARM had 19,780 food-poor fisherfolk in 2023, while Region VII recorded 22,310 in 2021. These are not dispersed cases but concentrated vulnerabilities requiring targeted intervention, with emphasis on both immediate food security and longer-term livelihood transformation.

Income realities. Official PSA data reports average monthly family income of ₱15,617.50 for the fisheries sector. However, this figure includes high-income commercial operators and aquaculture workers within the “skilled agricultural, forestry, and fishery workers” classification, significantly inflating the average and masking the economic reality of small-scale municipal fishers.

Field studies from Negros Oriental, Surigao del Sur, and Davao Gulf provide more accurate pictures of small-scale fisher income at the regional level: municipal fishers earn ₱2,591-5,697 per month, while commercial trawl owners earn ₱25,742. These are regional case studies, not national averages, but they reveal the stark income disparities within the sector. For a family living on ₱5,000 monthly or ₱167 per day—this falls well below both food poverty and general poverty thresholds.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Policy decisions made on averaged data that mask small-scale fisher poverty can lead to interventions that miss the most vulnerable populations. Understanding the actual income distribution—and recognizing that municipal fishers earn far less than national sector averages—is essential for effective program design and targeting support to those who need it most.

7.3 Government Support: Efforts and Mixed Outcomes

WHAT WE AUDITED: Scope, reach, and impact of government livelihood support programs for fisherfolk.

Program scope. Government has made substantial investments in fisher welfare:

- 509 million fingerlings distributed
- 1.29 million kg of seaweed provided
- 99,103 fishing gear sets delivered
- 6,321 boats provided
- 729 Community Fisherfolk Learning Centers established

The Special Area for Agricultural Development (SAAD) program specifically targeted

the 30 poorest provinces, demonstrating government commitment to reaching the most vulnerable communities.

Impact assessment. Available studies show mixed results. The FishCORAL Project evaluation (Ballesteros et al. 2025) found that its Fisheries, Coastal Resources, and Livelihood component in Region VIII did not significantly increase income and wealth of beneficiary households. However, Mamalangkap et al. (2016) documented that BFAR’s livelihood program in Jolo, Sulu, Tawi-tawi, and Basilan helped improve beneficiaries’ economic situations.

Analysis suggests that input distribution alone—boats, gear, fingerlings—does not necessarily transform underlying livelihood systems. Systemic issues include lack of comprehensive outcome monitoring, program fragmentation across multiple initiatives, and failure to scale up successful pilots. The persistence of high poverty rates despite substantial input distribution indicates that while effort is considerable, current approaches may need refinement to achieve transformative impact.

OUR ASSESSMENT: The government is investing resources and demonstrating commitment to fisherfolk welfare. The challenge is not lack of effort but the need to ensure programs are designed with sufficient attention to outcome measurement, replication of successes, and addressing root causes of poverty beyond input provision.

7.4 Women in Fisheries: Contribution and Representation Gaps

WHAT WE AUDITED: Women’s participation in fisheries and their representation in governance and support programs.

WHAT WE FOUND: Women represent 29-31% of registered fisherfolk, and this percentage has been declining. Women’s participation concentrates in specific sectors: fish vending (68%), intertidal gleaning (71%), and fish processing (70%). In capture fishing, women comprise only 9.4% of participants, and just 5% of census-counted operators.

Research indicates women are active throughout the fisheries value chain but face systematic inequalities: underrepresentation

in FARMCs and fishing cooperatives, proportionally less access to BFAR livelihood support, limited voice in decision-making processes, and exclusion from leadership positions.

Women depending on intertidal gleaning are particularly vulnerable to MPA restrictions yet remain underrepresented in MPA governance structures. Gender budgets allocated for women-specific programs often go unutilized, as documented in COA reports.

OUR ASSESSMENT: Women’s contributions to fisheries are substantial but inadequately recognized in policies, programs, and governance structures. Ensuring gender-inclusive approaches is both a matter of equity and management effectiveness—excluding 30% of the sector’s workforce from decision-making and support reduces the potential for successful outcomes.

7.5 Implications for National Food Security

Fish in the Filipino diet. Fish comprises 11.7% of typical Filipino food intake—the primary protein source, exceeding meat (7.2%) and poultry (3.8%) combined. Per capita consumption was 34.3 kg/year in 2018-2019, showing a declining trend from historical levels of 40 kg/year.

Municipal fisheries contribute approximately 13.97 kg per capita annually, representing about 38% of total fish consumption. As municipal capture fisheries decline, this contribution is at risk.

OUR ASSESSMENT: The decline of municipal fisheries has implications beyond fisher livelihoods—it affects national nutritional security. If domestic production continues

declining, the Philippines will face increased dependence on imported fish with associated cost implications for food accessibility among low-income populations.

7.6 Socioeconomic Status: Audit Summary

RESULT: Fisherfolk remain among the poorest basic sectors despite twenty years of programs and interventions. The 2023 poverty incidence of 27.4% (353,190 families) and food insecurity affecting 93,030 families indicate that current interventions, while substantial in scope, have not yet achieved transformative impact. The sector is aging with declining youth entry. Women's contributions are underrecognized. Government has demonstrated commitment through significant resource allocation; the challenge ahead is refining approaches to achieve lasting improvements in fisher welfare.

11.7%
FISH

7.2%
MEAT

3.8%
POULTRY

Fish comprises 11.7% of typical Filipino food intake—the primary protein source, exceeding meat (7.2%) and poultry (3.8%) combined.

CHAPTER 08

CONCLUSIONS

This assessment examined Philippine fisheries management from 2017 to 2024, focusing on implementation of RA 10654. The findings reveal a pattern: comprehensive legal frameworks exist, and substantial efforts are being made at multiple governance levels, yet ecological and socioeconomic outcomes have not shown measurable improvement.

8.1 Sustainability and Fisheries Management

STOCK STATUS:

- Since 2010, capture fisheries production has declined by approximately 45,472 metric tons annually
- Cumulative loss over 13 years (2010-2023): 591,136 metric tons
- National Stock Assessment Program: 88% of assessed stocks are overfished
- Scientific documentation of overfishing dates to the 1980s—this is not a recent development

MANAGEMENT RESPONSE: The government has implemented multiple interventions: 12 FMAs established with governance structures in place, seasonal fishing closures for key species, national management plans for tuna, sardines, blue swimming crab, and octopus, and over 2,100 MPAs designated. However, these interventions have yet to translate to measurable stock recovery. The management paradigm must shift from preventing overfishing to actively rebuilding depleted stocks, which requires more intensive and comprehensive measures than are currently in place.

8.2 Enforcement and Compliance

LEGAL FRAMEWORK: RA 10654 provides comprehensive provisions for enforcement, vessel monitoring, registration, and municipal water protection.

IMPLEMENTATION GAPS:

- Full implementation of VMM is stalled pending legal resolution
- Registration systems produce conflicting data (320,318 fisher discrepancy)
- 270,165 apparent illegal fishing detections in municipal waters (2017-2024) using VIIRS
- Only 1 of 174 LGUs authorizing commercial fishing complied with NAMRIA certification
- Estimated ₱5.4 billion lost to IUU fishing annually

ASSESSMENT: While legal frameworks are robust, implementation effectiveness is constrained by legal challenges (VMM suspension, Mercidar case), limited coordination between agencies, and insufficient resources for comprehensive enforcement. Resolving legal impediments and establishing the coordinated MCS system mandated by RA 10654 Section 7 amending RA 8550 Section 14 are priorities for strengthening compliance.

8.3 Institutional Capacity and Performance

BFAR ACHIEVEMENTS:

- Established all 12 FMAs with governance structures
- Issued 31 Fisheries Administrative Orders since 2015
- Implemented seasonal fishing closures and area-based management
- Enhanced international cooperation and reporting

CAPACITY CONSTRAINTS:

- 28% workforce loss (1,938 personnel) from 2017-2023
- 68% contractual workforce limits institutional continuity
- BFAR receives only 6-15% of Department of Agriculture budget
- COA reports document recurring unutilized funds and delayed program implementation
- Coordinated MCS system not established despite legal mandate

LGU IMPLEMENTATION:

- Only ~54% have ordinances addressing IUU fishing
- LGU penalty authority limited to ₱2,500 (vs. ₱5M in RA 10654)
- 51% lack delineated municipal water boundaries
- Bantay Dagat operates at approximately one-third of recommended budget

ASSESSMENT: Both national and local institutions face resource constraints that

limit implementation effectiveness. BFAR has demonstrated technical capacity and policy development capability despite staffing constraints. LGUs show willingness to manage fisheries locally. However, without adequate staffing, budget allocation, and coordination mechanisms, even well-designed policies struggle to achieve intended outcomes. Strengthening institutional capacity is foundational to effective fisheries management.

8.4 Fisherfolk Welfare

CURRENT STATUS:

- 353,190 fisherfolk families in poverty (27.4% incidence vs. 15.5% national average)
- 93,030 families in food insecurity
- Fisherfolk have been poorest or second-poorest basic sector for two decades
- Mean age 49-52 years; youth declining to enter fishing
- Women underrepresented in governance and inadequately supported

ASSESSMENT: Government has invested substantially in fisher welfare through multiple programs distributing boats, gear, fingerlings, and training. The persistence of high poverty rates despite these investments indicates that current approaches, while demonstrating commitment, have not achieved transformative impact. Programs may benefit from enhanced outcome monitoring, scaling successful models, and addressing structural barriers to fisher economic advancement beyond input distribution.

8.5 Overall Assessment

The assessment confirms that Philippine fisheries face persistent challenges: declining production, high overfishing rates, continued IUU fishing, and fisherfolk poverty.

The government has established legal frameworks, governance structures, and support programs that demonstrate awareness and commitment to addressing these challenges.

The central finding is not absence of effort but a gap between policy ambition and implementation capacity. This gap manifests in multiple ways: workforce declining while mandates expand, monitoring systems

suspended by legal challenges, unutilized budgets while needs persist, process metrics showing compliance while outcomes deteriorate, and local governments assigned responsibilities without adequate authority or resources.

Addressing these challenges will require coordinated action across multiple fronts: resolving legal impediments to monitoring systems, strengthening institutional capacity at national and local levels, ensuring resources match responsibilities, connecting process compliance to outcome achievement, and refining program approaches based on evidence of what works.

The Philippines has the policy framework and technical knowledge needed for sustainable fisheries management. The path forward involves translating existing policies into effective practice through adequate resourcing, institutional strengthening, and adaptive management that responds to evidence.

CHAPTER 09

RECOMMENDATIONS

These recommendations address the implementation gaps in fisheries management identified by the report. They are organized by priority area and designed to be actionable within current institutional structures. Success will require coordinated effort across government agencies, adequate resource allocation, and sustained political commitment.

PRIORITY 1

Resolve legal impediments to vessel monitoring. Expedite resolution of FAO 266 suspension and Mercidar case implications. Restore vessel monitoring capacity as soon as legally permissible.

PRIORITY 2

Harmonize registration systems. Reconcile discrepancies between PSA Census and FishR data. Clean registration lists of inactive fishers. Deploy mobile registration teams to remote coastal communities.

PRIORITY 3

Complete municipal water delineation. Focus on the 49% of LGUs lacking boundary delineation. Prioritize regions with highest fishing pressure and intrusion rates.

PRIORITY 4

Strengthen enforcement in hotspot areas. Deploy enhanced resources to FMAs 4, 5, and 11 where intrusion rates are highest. Support Bantay Dagat with immediate budget increases toward recommended levels.

9.2 Strengthening Institutional Capacity

BFAR Capacity:

1. **Reverse workforce decline:** Develop strategic hiring plan to address 28% personnel loss. Prioritize permanent positions over contractual arrangements to build institutional continuity.
2. **Increase budget allocation:** Advocate for BFAR to receive larger share of Department of Agriculture budget, commensurate with expanded RA 10654 mandates.
3. **Address COA findings:** Implement systems to ensure timely fund deployment, reduce unutilized budgets, and accelerate program implementation. Establish quarterly monitoring of budget execution rates.
4. **Reform performance metrics:** Shift from process-based to outcome-based indicators. Connect administrative performance ratings to ecological outcomes like stock recovery and reduced overfishing.
5. **Establish coordinated MCS:** Implement the Monitoring, Control, and Surveillance system mandated by RA 10654. Develop protocols for coordination with LGUs, PCG, PNP, and other agencies.

LGU Support:

1. **Technical assistance:** Deploy BFAR teams to support LGUs in ordinance updating, FARMC activation, and CRM plan implementation. Share best practices and successful models.
2. **Financial support:** Increase Bantay Dagat budgets toward recommended ₱1.2M per LGU. Support equipment acquisition for patrol boats, communication systems, and safety gear.
3. **Authority enhancement:** Explore mechanisms to enhance LGU penalty authority beyond ₱2,500/P3,000 limits, in municipalities and cities, respectively. Streamline processes for accessing national-level adjudication for serious violations.
4. **FARMC revitalization:** Provide resources for active operations. Ensure meaningful fisherfolk participation beyond token representation. Mandate regular meetings and reporting.

9.3 Enhancing Enforcement Effectiveness

1. **Implement vessel monitoring:** Once legal impediments are resolved, deploy VMM and electronic reporting systems for all commercial vessels. Establish data sharing protocols between agencies.
2. **Municipal water protection:** Enforce Section 18 requirements strictly. Ensure LGUs obtain NAMRIA certification before authorizing commercial fishing in 10.1-15km zone. Conduct public hearings with FARMCs. Verify clean violation records.
3. **Combat IUU fishing:** Strengthen prosecution of violations. Ensure swift case processing. Make penalties meaningful enough to deter repeat offenses. Support community-based monitoring.
4. **Data transparency:** Make consolidated stock assessment data publicly accessible. Establish regular update cycles. Use historical catch data (required since 1998) for management decisions.

9.4 Improving Management Effectiveness

1. **Strengthen FMAs:** Establish clear funding mechanisms for all 12 FMAs. Set definite implementation timelines. Enhance municipal fisher representation beyond token participation. Connect governance indicators to stock status outcomes.
2. **Implement Harvest Control Rules:** Finalize HCRs for all FMAs and priority species. Ensure HCRs are binding and automatically trigger management responses. Regular review and adjustment based on stock assessments.
3. **Scale and strengthen MPAs:** Assess current MPA effectiveness. Develop ecologically coherent networks. Ensure adequate enforcement resources. Address equity in benefits and governance.
4. **Comprehensive interventions:** Recognize that closed seasons alone are insufficient. Implement complementary measures: limit overall fishing effort, protect critical habitats, provide alternative livelihoods, and ensure strong community engagement.

9.5 Improving Fisherfolk Welfare

1. **Transform livelihood programs:** Move beyond input distribution to comprehensive livelihood transformation. Implement rigorous outcome monitoring. Scale up programs with proven success. Reduce fragmentation across initiatives.
2. **Economic empowerment:** Provide access to credit, insurance, and post-harvest

facilities. Support fisher cooperatives to increase bargaining power. Develop market infrastructure to reduce middleman exploitation.

3. **Social protection:** Ensure fisherfolk access to PhilHealth, SSS, and medical services. Conduct information campaigns on fisher rights, safety at sea, and disaster preparedness.
4. **Gender equity:** Recognize women's contributions throughout the value chain. Ensure gender-inclusive registration and program access. Increase women's representation in FARMCs and cooperatives. Utilize gender budgets that currently remain unspent.
5. **Youth engagement:** Address factors deterring youth entry: improve economic conditions, provide advancement opportunities, reduce risks, create stability. Ensure intergenerational knowledge transfer.
6. **Alternative livelihoods:** Provide genuine alternatives to reduce fishing pressure on depleted stocks. Ensure transition support includes training and start-up capital. Make alternatives economically viable.

9.6 Strengthening Knowledge Systems and Transparency

1. **Expand stock assessments:** Increase coverage beyond currently assessed stocks. Establish regular assessment cycles. Make data publicly accessible in consolidated, updated databases.
2. **Close data gaps:** Prioritize municipal sector data collection. Integrate local ecological knowledge. Support community-based monitoring.

3. **Public reporting:** Establish annual public reporting on fisheries status. Include stock assessments, enforcement statistics, program outcomes, and progress toward RA 10654 objectives.
4. **Adaptive management:** Use evidence to refine approaches. Scale successes. Discontinue or redesign ineffective programs. Regular evaluation and adjustment based on outcomes.

9.7 The Path Forward

Philippine fisheries stand at a critical juncture. The challenges are substantial with 88% of assessed stocks overfished, 591,136 metric tons lost over 13 years, and 353,190 fisherfolk families living in poverty. However, the foundations for recovery exist: comprehensive legal frameworks, established governance structures, demonstrated government commitment, and technical expertise.

What is needed is not new policies but effective implementation of existing ones. This requires adequate resourcing. What does this look like? It means matching workforce and budgets to expanded mandates. It requires coordination: establishing the MCS system that connects agencies and closes enforcement gaps. It requires accountability: shifting from process metrics to outcome measurement. It requires persistence: sustaining effort over years and political cycles.

88%

**ASSESSED STOCKS
OVERFISHED**

591,136 mt

FISH LOST OVER 13 YEARS

353,129

**FISHERFOLK FAMILIES
LIVING IN POVERTY**

The government has demonstrated willingness to address fisheries challenges through legislation, program development, and resource allocation. This assessment identifies areas where current approaches can be strengthened and made more effective. Success will require sustained commitment, adaptive management based on evidence, and coordination across all levels of governance.

Recovery is possible, if it is implemented across the board. The biological capacity for

COMPREHENSIVE LEGAL FRAMEWORKS, ESTABLISHED GOVERNANCE STRUCTURES, DEMONSTRATED GOVERNMENT COMMITMENT, AND TECHNICAL EXPERTISE.

stock rebuilding exists if fishing pressure is reduced. The institutional framework for management exists if adequately resourced. The political commitment exists if translated into sustained implementation. The path forward is clear: what remains is walking it with sufficient urgency and coordination to achieve the outcomes that Filipino fisherfolk, coastal communities, and the nation need and deserve.

Note on Future Assessments: This assessment is intended as the first in a regular series. Subsequent assessments will track progress on these recommendations and evaluate whether implementation efforts are translating into improved ecological and socioeconomic outcomes. Regular assessment provides accountability and enables adaptive management based on evidence of what works.

Technical Report: This narrative report distills findings from the technical assessment Philippine Fisheries Assessment: A Glimpse of RA 10654's 10-Year Implementation by Alice Joan G. Ferrer, Wilfredo L. Campos, and Harold M. Monteclaro. Access the full technical report with detailed data and methodology at ph.oceana.org

OCEANA

PH.OCEANA.ORG

NET LOSS: HOW GOVERNANCE GAPS
ARE SINKING PHILIPPINE FISHERIES

